

HISTORY OF ICE CREAM PRODUCTION

Nurmatova Nodira Nazirovna

Food technology and engineering in Fergana

International Institute of Kokan Food Industry and Service

teacher of the technical school

Abstract: *This article describes the history of ice cream, its real product, and its preparation processes*

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Ice cream, which has a history of about five thousand years, is distinguished by its high value even in today's ranking of sweets. In almost all countries, ice cream is considered a dessert or treat, served as a separate dish and eaten in combination with coffee, milkshakes, pastries, jam, jam, fruits.

Ice cream is a dessert, and although its history is unknown, there are several sources of its origin. Some sources describe ice-cream-like treats originating in Persia around 550 BC, [1.2] [3.2] while other sources state that the Roman emperor Nero collected ice from the Apennine Mountains to make the first sorbet, a mixture of honey and wine, which is now known as sorbet dessert. It is believed to have been prepared for the first time in Persia. [4.3][3.2][5.4][6.5][7.6] According to other sources, ice cream originated in the Mongol Empire and first spread to China during the expansion of the Mongol Empire's borders.[8.7] So, according to some sources, the history of ice cream is about five thousand years. It is also stated that it started years ago, that a similar dessert existed in ancient China, and in those days it was served on the table mixed with snow or ice, orange, lemon slices or pomegranate seeds.

Ice cream is a popular dessert for people of all ages, both children and adults love to eat it. A wide range allows everyone to enjoy their favorite taste:

- pure and additive filler
- ice cream with milk and cream
- fruit and chocolate, in a waffle cup and with chocolate glaze. Therefore, the

technology of its preparation is an interesting process for everyone.

The ice cream production process is mainly carried out in 2 stages. The first stage includes ingredients, homogenization, sterilization, cooling and cooking, while the second stage mainly covers the freezing, forming and solidification processes.

The recycling process is as follows:

- mixing raw materials → filtering → homogenizing → sterilization → cooling → adding spices → cooking → freezing → filling → solidification → packaging → storage.

Ice cream is made from eggs, cream or various fruits. Ice cream requires first the preparation of the main ingredient combination and the process of freezing the combination. For creamy ice cream, eggs or egg yolks are mixed with sugar, and when the sugar dissolves, hot milk is poured in and it is continuously stirred with a whisk. A well-mixed thick mass will form in the bowl. Vanillin is added to it, then it is poured into molds, cooled and frozen.

To get 1 kg of ice cream, the following ingredients (in grams) are needed:

- milk 600
- cream 75
- sugar 250
- vanillin 0.1
- 3 eggs.

For fruit ice cream, the fruit is boiled and then passed through a wire sieve and pureed. Sugar is dissolved in boiling water. After the mixture cools down, it is mixed with puree and put into molds and frozen.

For 1 kg of fruit ice cream, the following quantity is required:

- 200 g of fruit (strawberries, tangerines, etc.)
- 325 g of sugar
- 1 g of citric acid is needed. [8]

Below is the technology for making chocolate ice cream:

- Chocolate is broken and pieces are put in milk.
- The milk container is put on the minimum heat, the chocolate is completely melted
- Sugar is added, a little salt is added
- Crystals are completely dissolved.
- With hot milk, whites are constantly mixed with separated eggs.
- Vanilla is added, all ingredients are combined.
- The finished mass is left to cool. Ice cream is frozen in the chamber.

The following ingredients are needed to make chocolate ice cream:

- dark chocolate - 125 g;
- milk - 240 ml;
- eggs - 2.4
- saturated sugar - 145 g;
- fat cream - 260 ml;
- vanilla plate;
- sea salt;
- a handful of pecans.

In conclusion, the main ingredients of ice cream are various dairy products, whole milk, skim milk, cheese, butter, condensed milk powder and dry milk, as

well as sugar, stabilizer, emulsifier, flavor enhancer and coloring agent. It is important to say that it is permissible to draw attention. A good quality stabilizer should be added for good ice cream.

We recommend that you learn the main functions of the ice cream stabilizer in the production of ice cream:

1. Improve emulsion stability and prevent whey separation and precipitation.
2. Improve the performance of the inflatable, increase the speed of foaming and expansion.
3. Prevent or control the growth of ice crystals during storage, delay melting, improve storage stability, and prevent shrinkage and deformation of finished products.
4. Improving the formation and structure of the finished ice cream.
5. Improve shape retention, extend food shelf life and improve mouth solubility.

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